

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT FOR OPERATIONS IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY IN VIETNAM: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON EFFECTIVE AND RELIABLE HAZOP ASSESSMENT

Vo Viet Hai (DBA Student)

Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) | School of Management

Willi Zimmermann (Supervisor)

Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) | School of Management

INTRODUCTION

Offshore oil and gas (OO&G) production rigs aim to explore and exploit crude oil & gas from seabed to surface rigs then transport to shore or storage tank facilities. Due to operating offshore, these rigs face various risks and hazards (ISO 19901, 2015; ISO 17776, 2016), hence two critical subjects: Risk Management (RM) and Operations Management (OM) are always particularly focused on.

Among methods to identify engineering HAZard and OPerability (HAZOP), a qualitative method named “HAZOP Assessment”, or “HAZOP Study” has become a mandatory procedure for risk identifications of any OO&G rig (EU Directive, 2013; James G., 2015; DNVGL-RP-N101, 2017). HAZOP Studies are formal systematic and experienced-based examination focusing on engineering intentions of new or existing systems to evaluate the hazard potential of mal-operation or malfunction of individual systems’ items which can be consequential effects on the complete system(s) (IEC 61892, 2016; DNV-SE-479, 2021). Dennis N. (2016) reported that 80% of projects’ hazard analysis processes were conducted via this method.

Due to HAZOP Study’s importance, its effectiveness and reliability are critical objectives in academic and practical research. With arguing that knowledge is the center of HAZOP Study activities, this research focus on the issues of Knowledge Acquisition (KA) and Knowledge Management (KM) to ensure the effectiveness and reliability of HAZOP Studies in the context of the Vietnam OO&G industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to BS ISO 30401 (2022), scope of KM consists of acquisition, analysis, sharing, transferring and applications. To deeply understand HAZOP KA/KM, we first study how HAZOP knowledge is acquired and managed in traditional methodology.

KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION IN TRADITIONAL HAZOP STUDY

Theoretically, traditional HAZOP Study is a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) (Fentahun A., 2021), through which qualitative HAZOP knowledge is acquired from a HAZOP Study team. This team is collected from multi-discipline experts for a short-time workshop under facilitation of expertise facilitator(s) (Dennis N., 2016; Frank C. et al., 2015). Major inputs for HAZOP workshop are process and instrumentation diagrams (P&IDs) which are representations for engineering systems and consist of two basic components: system requirements and the physical/logical descriptions of systems' design (IEC 61892, 2016).

The process of a HAZOP Study is a “*guide word examination*”. In HAZOP workshop, HAZOP experts examine each segment of the P&IDs, then together brainstorming, searching deliberately keywords, and identifying qualitative “*deviations*” e.g. “*low flow*”, “*high pressure*” from the current design intents which become possible “*causes*” of hazards in operations. They also analyze “*consequences*” of the hazard, then determine if there is any protection method called “*safeguard*” provided to mitigate negative effect of the hazard. If not, they will propose “*recommendations*” for appropriate safeguards (WGT, 2015; Dennis N., 2016; BV, 2023). A sample of HAZOP Study process for a simplified pump system illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: HAZOP Assessment sample and verbal transcript

“Operator: Oh no now the upstream piping is leaking. I better close this off again and figure out what's going on.”

Expert A: There is a spec brake immediately upstream of the pump high pressure fluid from the running pump A traveled back through the second trip to pump B to the suction side...

Expert B: I thought check valves were meant to prevent reverse flow. There is one at the discharge of each pump.

Expert C: check valves are directional valves that should be able to block flow in the reverse direction and are often installed downstream of pumps to improve pumping efficiency unfortunately they can leak or become stuck open”.

(Source: Icarus-ORM Academy, 2020)

From the verbal transcript, HAZOP facilitator(s) and Note-taker identify and code “the upstream piping is leaking” as “*Consequence C.1*”; “high pressure fluid from the running pump A traveled back” as *Deviation “Reverse Flow D.1*”; And “check valves” as “*Safeguard S.1*” to mitigate the deviation D.1; “Check valve can leak or become stuck open” is verified as “*Possible Cause P.1*” of the Deviation D.1.

The outcomes of process are sets of HAZOP knowledge in form of “*deviation*”, “*cause*”, “*consequence*”, “*safeguard*” and “*recommendation*” which are recorded into IEC standardized HAZOP worksheets.

KNOWLEDGE VALIDATIONS IN TRADITIONAL HAZOP STUDY

The value of a HAZOP Study relies on the completeness and adequacy of input documents. Hence, the HAZOP team first must review and validate documents to ensure they accurately represent the system (IEC 61892, 2016). These required in-depth knowledge of experts to understand the complex design intents.

Second, to ensure HAZOP knowledge trustworthiness, as an FGD, facilitator(s) often conduct some tactics to focus HAZOP team on discussion e.g. “Staying on track”, “Quality control for scribing”, “No designing” (BV, 2023). These tactics aim to prevent the biases, group thinking and accuracies of feedback (Miles et al., 2014), or lack of systemizing in data interpretations (Frank C. et al., 2015; Dennis N., 2016).

And last, to validate the completeness of HAZOP Study, after workshop, HAZOP facilitator(s) often conduct several rounds of validations, then finalize findings by HAZOP Close-out Report (BV, 2023).

KNOWLEDGE VERIFICATION IN TRADITIONAL HAZOP STUDY

As a formal procedure, Register(s) e.g. DNV, BV, LR, always review and verify HAZOP Study Reports (DNVGL-RP-N101, 2017; DNV-SE-479, 2021) to ensure

risks/hazards have been fully identified, safeguards have been provided in compliance with mandatory safety-related regulations and standards.

SUMMARIZATIONS

The traditional HAZOP KA/KM focus on acquisition, validation and verification of knowledge. Experts are center of the studies to brainstorm and provide knowledge through verbal transcripts. Such processes usually do not encounter any issues when the HAZOP team members and facilitators are still working together.

PROBLEM STATEMENTS

Although the traditional FGD HAZOP Study has become a standardized procedure, its approach always requires mandatorily participation of multi-disciplinary experts for *brainstorming to build verbal transcripts*, then analyzing and interpreting to acquire HAZOP knowledge. But the approach is cause of the problems:

- First, the IEC 61892 (2016), which is formal standard for HAZOP application guide, has admitted the *limitations of HAZOP studies are greatly if not most fully relying on the knowledge, systemic abilities, experiences, and interaction of HAZOP team members*. This is the main challenge for KM, levels of completeness, efficiency, uncertainty, and vagueness of HAZOP knowledge (Jing W. et al., 2018).
- Second, acquiring through workshop and relying on individual interpretations are causes of difficulties in validating HAZOP knowledge afterward. It raises the concerns on *ensuring trustworthiness of this knowledge over the 30 years life cycle of OO&G system*.
- Third, due to acquiring from a dedicated team for specific systems, traditional HAZOP knowledge is difficult to reuse, even for standardized OO&G systems e.g. Compressor or Waste Heat Recovery which almost have the same design intents. No reusing fully or partly this knowledge not only time and cost consuming but also presents a *gap in Knowledge Management System (KMS) in which sharing and transferring knowledge should be managed* (BS ISO 30401, 2022).

Various academic research has recognized these problems exceedingly early, for instance:

- Kletz (1999) emphasized the significance of the team's collective knowledge and experience in identifying potential hazards during HAZOP study.
- Mannan (2012) and Crawley et al. (2015) highlighted the importance of assembling a team with comprehensive knowledge to ensure a thorough understanding of process and its potential hazards.

- Some recent scholarly articles have delved into the application of AI techniques in HAZOP KA, utilizing AI-based methods such as natural language processing (Xiayuan et al., 2021; Ali E. et al., 2023), or Bayesian algorithms and neural networks (Huaqi et al., 2023).

These studies often stress the important roles of *the knowledge base in traditional HAZOP Studies*, then provide guidance on way for assembling expertise teams or using modern support tools to ensure a comprehensive and effective analysis or automate these studies for more effective in practice.

RESEARCH OBJECT, SUBJECTS AND OBJECTIVES

As an empirical study, our research object is a new *OO&G rig named KNT* belonging to V-company in Vietnam. Under facilitation of Bureau Veritas (BV) Register, V-company had organized a FGD HAZOP Study in Jul 2023. BV has validated and verified the KNT HAZOP Study Report in Aug 2023.

Ensuring effectiveness and reliability of HAZOP Study through KA/KM is our general research objective. But from literature review, we are going to focus on two critical KM objectives are the *dependence on expert for KA* and the *trustworthiness of this acquired knowledge*. These objectives are studied in the contexts: system's 30-year life cycle, systems' complexities, multi-disciplinary knowledge, and role of company's KMS. And as a pilot study, we will conduct research for a system named Waste Heat Recovery System (WHRS), a complex heat transfer system to serve energy savings and emission reducing strategies.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research object and subject are same as traditional method, but with two above focal objectives, our research aims to shift away from the FGD approach and propose a new methodology to acquire and manage HAZOP knowledge more effectively and reliably with the two following main research questions:

1. *What are the strategies for enhancing KA and KM throughout by reducing dependence on experts?*
2. *What techniques can be employed to validate and substantiate knowledge during acquisition and application to ensure the trustworthiness of acquired knowledge?*

Extra research questions will ably identify additionally during developments of research methodology.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Through a Special Study, we have noted that KNT have pre-existing multi-disciplinary documents which contain rich and comprehensive data in 70 specifications and philosophies, 54 calculations and simulations, 166 data sheets, thousands of

drawings, and hundreds of referred regulations and standards (KNT-002 EMDR, 2023). Hence, we aim to use these documents as secondary data to exploit knowledge for HAZOP Study with research methodology as figured in Figure 2 and described as follow:

Figure 2. MDL-SE methodology for KA, building Knowledge Base and KM

- The core perspective is to shift the focus from expert-centric to a structured, systemized and document-based approach, which could increase the effectiveness, reliability and reusability of HAZOP knowledge.
- The methodology will integrate Multiple Document Literacy (MDL) with Systems Engineering (SE) techniques to improve KA/KM practices. Using MDL aims to supplant traditional expert-centric KA by acquiring knowledge from secondary verified document sources. SE provides standardized processes e.g. analysis, validation in which inputs-outputs and system-based activities are clearly defined and control. SE also introduces a quantitative model-based and systematic way to validate the trustworthiness of qualitative HAZOP knowledge through its relationships (Nicole et al., 2023).
- In addition, a combination of appropriate software e.g. MAXQDA will offer facilities to speed up analytic processes and manage multiple documents. Especially, it allows utilizing AI-based integrated tools of modern software to enhance analysis and management of knowledge.
- The HAZOP KA/KM will be conducted by KM team in company's KMS who have basic knowledge about the system, good understanding

about SE processes e.g. analysis, validations, integrations and will be responsible for KA/KM in the whole systems' life cycle. Consequently, the KA/KM will not only be relying on a small group of experts like in short-time traditional HAZOP workshops.

- The participation of experts is not fully eliminated or refused. Anytime an undefined knowledge called "*Null knowledge*" found, through KMS, KM team or even End-users of organizations can send it back to multi-discipline expertise team for in-depth study and problem solving.

In other words, the integration of MDL document-driven KA, SE system-based validation and qualitative analytic software will add further credibility to the methodology and enhance KA and KM, as well as overcoming the limitations of traditional human-reliance processes. Through the MDL-SE methodology, HAZOP knowledge becomes a knowledge base which is more structured, reliable, and manageable throughout the life cycle of OO&G systems.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design for solving two research questions will be carried out as follow.

REDUCING DEPENDENCE ON EXPERTS

The following tactical tasks are designed to implement MDL-SE HAZOP KA.

Document collections and validations: Same as traditional method, the first task of MDL-SE methodology is validating document inputs for HAZOP Study. We have applied perspectives of Stromso H. et al. (2013), Oistein A. et al. (2014), Morgan H. (2022) for validating documents of MDL method, through which we have assessed KNT documents for 04 criteria: "*authenticity*", "*representativeness*", "*credibility*" and "*meaning*" as follow.

- Regarding the documents' *representativeness*, a vast number of multi-disciplinary documents have been developed to serve whole stages of design, procurement, fabrication, construction, operations, and maintenance of the KNT systems. These multi-disciplinary documents have fully described whole engineering processes, specifications, design intents, safety and operational philosophies, modelling, and calculations. In other words, the documents are representative of the actual systems.
- Regarding the document's *meaning and content*, on one hand, the system's documents have been developed in the way they fully meet the systems' engineering performances, social and economic requirements expected by stakeholders. On the other hand, their contents must comply with cross-disciplinary criteria as required in regulations and standards e.g. DNV-SE-0479 (2017); DNV-OS-D202 (2021). As a result, the documents are well-standardized and richly contained not only managerial

and engineering data but also safety requirements related to risk/hazard management.

- Regarding to documents' *authenticity and credibility*, in compliance with nominated standards e.g. ISA, IEC, ISO, whole O&G systems' documents are standardized and systemized to ensure each document provides correctly necessary data for its purposes, as well as controllable in systems' life cycle. Especially, all safety-related documents of the O&G documentation system must be reviewed and approved, as well as frequently audited and verified by Registers.

Hence, these documents are eligible and especially appropriate for methods aiming to exploit data from pre-existing documents like MDL.

Document analysis: Same as traditional FGD method, we use P&IDs as base to start risks/hazards identifications. Based on P&ID's identifications for systems' elements e.g. valve, pump, and engineering processes e.g. mass-heat transfer, we will carry out analysis on whole relevant text documents and regulations/standards in KNT EMDR (2023) to identify risk/hazard-related data on these elements.

The text-based document analysis is carried out through keywords in the same way as common qualitative research. Manually or using software, we will implement the searching deliberate keywords, analyzing, coding chunks of HAZOP-related meanings in documents then manual or automatic extract them into preliminary HAZOP Study Report in form of Excel worksheet like traditional FGD method.

To trial test and develop the research methodology, we will apply the MDL-SE text-based analysis for HAZOP assessment on WHRS. A sample of manual analysis on document named Control Philosophy of WHRS of the KNT is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Sample of MDL text-based analysis

This is where the qualitative research approach like MDL combined with SE comes into play. The qualitative studies can be conducted at the descriptive level: Rather than focus on interpreting latent meaning, researchers look for explicit meaning in the data of documents (Bowen, 2009; Morgan, 2022). Based on specific themes of HAZOP study called “*Nodes*” e.g. for Hot Oil Pump segment in Fig. 3, chunks of respective meanings in the text are colored codes by keywords e.g. “Deviation D-1, D-2”, “Consequence C-1, C-2”; those codes that appear often are kept and used in the further analyses particularly in the analysis of relations among them (Kuckartz, 2014; Miles et al., 2014; Creswell et al., 2021).

The outcomes of MDL-SE HAZOP Study are also sets of HAZOP knowledge, but it is extracted from text-based analysis, not from verbal transcripts like in traditional FGD HAZOP.

VALIDATING THE ACQUIRED KNOWLEDGE TRUSTWORTHINESS

First, in principle of company’s Document Control System, documents in KNT EMDR (2023) have been always reviewed and validated internally by a multi-discipline team, and externally by a Third Party, who is DNV Register in the KNT case. Same as role of “Third party Decision-maker” or “External auditor” in qualitative research (Miles et al., 2014; Creswell et al., 2021), the Third Party is responsible for ensuring the trustworthiness and eligibility of the documents. Hence, with MDL-SE strategy, the HAZOP knowledge trustworthiness will be naturally inherited from the pre-existing trustworthiness of validated documents.

Second, to actively validate and substantiate the HAZOP knowledge during KA and KM without or less participation of experts, we will apply math-physics model-based techniques and system-based analytic/validated processes of SE (ISO IEC IEEE 15288, 2023; IncoSE, 2023) to secure the relationships and trustworthiness of the acquired knowledge. For instance, to validate relationships and trustworthiness between C-1 & D-1 in example Fig. 1, instead of validation through brainstorming of HAZOP experts, we can use Bernoulli Equation which describes relation between flow and pressure, then assign HAZOP keywords e.g. “*high flow*”, “*less flow*”, “*high pressure*” on the corresponding variables in equation to interpret qualitative explicit meaning. Such equations are presented in Mass Balance Calculations of pre-existing design documents. The HAZOP safeguard(s) will be identified, evaluated and advised through analyzing standards e.g. API 14 series (2017) applied for the concerned system.

In other words, applying SE techniques will introduce a new layer of analysis which is more rigorous and quantitative to traditional expert-driven qualitative processes. Hence, it is not only reducing dependence on human experts on validating knowledge trustworthiness, but also systematically consolidating expertise knowledge for researcher(s) in KM team.

And last, due to the KNT's traditional HAZOP Study Report having been completed, we will compare both knowledge trustworthiness of FGD and MDL-SE HAZOP Study Reports each other via triangulation method (Miles et al, 2014; Creswell et al, 2021) to ensure the quality of both research methodologies.

GENERALIZATION OF RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Through a Special Study in 2023, we have noted that 100% practical HAZOP Studies at OO&G Vietnam companies have been implemented through traditional FGD method. Hence, an additional research question raised: *How to ensure the generalization of the MDL-SE methodology to apply for other O&G companies outside of V-Company in HAZOP KA and KM domains.*

Reviewing HAZOP Reports and input documents of other companies, we have noted that the overall object, subject, challenges, and objectives in HAZOP Assessments are the same and standardized in OO&G companies. Together with this, we also recognize that:

- First, regarding document inputs: It is confirmed that the whole O&G project's documents are always developed in accordance with mandatory regulations and standards. Then whole documents must be reviewed and validated internally and externally to ensure they are complying with applicable regulations and standards, as well as well-controlled, managed and updated in their life cycle. Hence, they are always appropriate for MDL-SE strategies.
- Second, regarding MDL-SE tasks, through common MDL and SE analytic techniques, HAZOP knowledge is analyzed in compliance with IEC 61892 standardized keywords e.g. "deviation", "consequence". Hence, the analytic and coding processes on any text-based documents are totally the same for any company.

Hence, although conducting the research at V-Company, we have tried to ensure the generalization of the methodology through a generalized flowchart for MDL-SE KA/KM as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Flowchart of Research (Source: Adapted from Hai LX & Hai VV, 2023)

In flowchart, steps from 1 to 5 are general for companies. From step 6 to 8, HAZOP KM team will apply the MDL-SE methodology for data collection, analysis, and validations based on specific input documents; Third Parties verify outcomes at step 9; Conclusions made at step 10. The re-validating tasks of each research step will be conducted through steps from 7.1 to 7.4. At step 7.4, researcher(s) can re-validate the research objectives to verify if the new methodology is not appropriate to apply for his research. Through step 11, researcher(s) can utilize pre-existing knowledge from other eligible sources e.g. regulations, standards or experienced data from other companies to validate each step's outcomes.

Obviously, although the research is developed in specific V-Company's context, the MDL-SE methodology is generalization and can be applied for other O&G companies on specific input documents.

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

First, regarding academic implication, through MDL approach, the methodology reduces dependence on human experts by focusing on text-based document analysis through which ensures knowledge acquisition is systematically rather than relying on individuals. Integrating a rigor from SE's model- and system-based approaches, the methodology is not only increasing the knowledge trustworthiness but also makes the knowledge more reliable and easier to validate, as well as easier to communicate findings to relevant disciplinary teams and managers over long-life cycle of the OO&G systems.

Second, for practical applications, the MDL-SE can be applied independently, but it can be also used as consolidated method to explicate latent meanings and enhance trustworthiness of experts' HAZOP knowledge which has been acquired though traditional FGD.

And last, for managerial implication, through MDL-SE, HAZOP knowledge becomes a database linked to specific document sources and managed by KMS over system's life cycle. Anytime occurring any changes in these documents, KM team is simply revisiting the updated documents, identifying the HAZOP-related changed portions, re-analyzing and re-validating, then updating HAZOP knowledge database.

CONCLUSIONS

The MDL-SE methodology is a combination of qualitative MDL text-based analysis with SE and computer-based software for enhancing effectiveness and reliability of HAZOP assessment for OO&G systems. The MDL-SE methodology can overcome drawbacks of the traditional FGD method and provides a new potential approach for HAZOP KA/KM in the whole OO&G systems' life cycle.

Although the foreseen disadvantage of MDL-SE is time consuming for establishing procedures, trainings and conducting KA and KM. But obviously, with advantages e.g. trustworthy knowledge, a knowledge database which is manageable, reusable, and accessible throughout a long-life cycle, the expenses for the MDL-SE development are justified for OO&G applications. Moreover, with the combination of smart and AI-based analytic modules in appropriate software, these disadvantages can be re-solved when the methodology is invested appropriately.

In conclusion, the MDL-SE methodology offers a promising approach to improve KA and KM in HAZOP Assessment. The methodology should be studied further more at company level and higher, as well as incorporating advancements of AI-

based techniques to enhance its potential advantages for both safety and operational efficiency of complex OO&G industry over its life cycle.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Ali E., Mehrdad B., Davood R. (2023). Application of natural language processing and machine learning in prediction of deviations in the HAZOP study worksheet. A comparison of classifiers. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*. 0957-5820. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2023.06.004>
- API 14 Series (2017). *API Standards for Safe Offshore Operations*. American Petroleum Institute.
- Bowen G.A. (2009). Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method. *Qualitative Research Journal*, Vol. 9 No. 2, pp. 27-40. <https://doi.org/10.3316/QRJ0902027>
- BS ISO 30401 (2022). *Knowledge management systems — Requirements*. International Organization for Standardization. ISBN 978 0 539 12673 0.
- Bureau Veritas BV (2023). *HAZOP Study Procedure*. Bureau Veritas Register.
- Creswell J.W, Baez J.C (2021). *30 essential skills for the qualitative researcher*. SAGE Publications. ISBN 9781544355733.
- Dennis N.P (2016). *Safety and Security Review for the Process Industry. Application of HAZOP, PHA, What-IF and SVA Reviews*. Elsevier Inc. ISBN: 978-0-323-32295-9.
- DNVGL RP-N101 (2017). *Risk management in marine and subsea operations*. DNV GL AS.
- DNV-SE-0479 (2021). *Verification of process facilities*. DNV AS.
- EU Directive (2013). *Directive of The European Parliament and the Council of 12 June 2013 on safety of offshore oil and gas operations and amending Directive 2004/35/EC*. Official Journal of the European Union. L 178/66
- Fentahun A. Y. (2021). *Focus Group Discussion as a data collection tool in Economics*. Daagu International Journal of Basic & Applied Research DIJBAR. Volume3, Issue-1, pp (52-61). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352817078>
- Frank Crawley, Brian T. (2015). *HAZOP: Guide to Best Practice. Guidelines to Best Practice for the Process and Chemical Industries*. Third Edition. Elsevier. ISBN: 978-0-323-39460-4
- Hai LX., Hai VV. (2023). *Systems Approach. Basic concepts and interpretations in chemical and oil and gas engineering*. VNUHCM Press. ISBN 978-604-479-028-2.
- Huaqi Z., Beike Z., Dong G. (2023). A new approach of integrating industry prior knowledge for HAZOP interaction. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*. 82-105005. 0950-4230 Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2023.105005>
- Icarus-ORM Academy (2020). *Reverse Flow Overpressure - A HAZOP Crash Course*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y2NRMmW4LiQ>.
- IEC 61882 (2016). *Hazard and operability studies (HAZOP studies) – Application guide*. The International Electrotechnical Commission. ISBN 978-2-8322-3208-8.

- IncoSE (2023). *Systems Engineering Handbook*. Fifth Edition. INCOSE-TP-2003-002-05 2023.
- ISO 17776 (2016). *Petroleum and natural gas industries - Offshore production installations - Major accident hazard management during the design of new installations*. ISO.
- ISO 19901 (2015). *Petroleum and natural gas industries - Specific requirements for offshore structures - Part 1: Metocean design and operating considerations*. ISO.
- ISO IEC IEEE 15288 (2023). *Systems and software engineering. System life cycle processes*. The British Standards Institution. ISBN 9780539169188.
- James G. S. (2015). *Handbook of Offshore Oil and Gas Operations*. Elsevier. ISBN 978-1-85617-558-6.
- Jing W., M. Lind (2018). *Management of System Complexity in HAZOP for the Oil & Gas Industry*. 2405-8963 IFAC. Papers OnLine 51-8. 211-216. 10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.06.379
- KNT-002 EMDR (2023). *Engineering Master Deliverable Register*. V-Company.
- Kuckartz U. (2014). *Qualitative Text Analysis*. SAGE Publications Ltd. ISBN 978-1-4462-6774-5
- Mannan, S. (2012). *Lees' Loss Prevention in the Process Industries: Hazard Identification, Assessment, and Control*. 4th Edition. Elsevier. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-397189-0.00001-X>
- Miles B.M., Huberman A.M, Saldaña J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis. A Method Sourcebook*. SAGE Publication Inc. ISBN 978-1-4522-5787-7.
- Morgan, H. (2022). Conducting a Qualitative Document Analysis. *The Qualitative Report*, 27(1), 64-77. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2022.5044>
- Nicole H., Chris H., Gary S., Jeffrey C., Tom McD., Bernardo D., Art P., Clif B., Daniel De., Robert J. C., Garry R. (2023). *Guide to the Systems Engineering Body of Knowledge (SEBoK), version 2.9*. www.sebokwiki.org.
- Oistein Anmarkrud, Ivar Breten,, Helge I. Stromso (2014). Multiple-documents literacy. Strategic processing, source awareness, and argumentation when reading multiple conflicting documents. *Learning and Individual Differences* 30. 64-76. 1041-6080 Elsevier. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2013.01.007>
- Strømsø, H.I., & Bråten, I. (2013). Multiple documents literacy. In L.H. Meyer (Ed.), *Oxford Bibliographies in Education*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Trevor Kletz (1999). *Hazop and Hazan_ Identifying and assessing process industry hazards*. IChem Four Edition. ISBN 10-0-85295-506-5.
- Wise Global Training WGT (2015). *Introduction to Oil and Gas Operational Safety*. Routledge. ISBN-10: 0-415-73077-5.
- Xiayuan F., Yiyang D., Xu J., Li Z., Yagu D. (2021). Application of natural language processing in HAZOP reports. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection* 155, 41-48. 0957-5820 Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2021.09.001>